

Youth Survey Results Collected for Analysis

Joan Ribas Serra, Enric Bas, Mario Guilló, Estrella Tobará-Rodrigo, Vinicius Martini Capovilla, and Amanda Barba Martínez. March 31, 2026. Version No. 1.0.

D3.2 Overview

PROJECT	RELISH
PROJECT NO.	101177427
WORKPACKAGE	WP3: INGREDIENTS
DELIVERABLE	D3.2
VERSION NO.	1.0
DUE DATE	31/03/2026
SUBMISSION DATE	31/03/2026
TYPE	Public
AUTHOR(S)	Joan Ribas Serra, Enric Bas, Mario Guilló, Estrella Tobara-Rodrigo, Vinicius Martini Capovilla, and Amanda Barba Martínez
REVIEWER(S)	Janita Van Dyk, Andrea Borghini, Christian Reynolds, Maxime Michaud
APPROVER	H. Rosi Song

Document history

VERSION	DATE	AUTHOR(S)	CHANGES
0.1	10/03/2026	Joan Ribas Serra	Document creation
0.2	13/03/2026	Joan Ribas Serra, Enric Bas, Mario Guilló, Vinicius Martini Capovilla, Amanda Barba Martínez	Draft 0.2
0.3	13/03/2026	Janita Van Dyk	Draft 0.3: WP1 preliminary review and figures
0.4	18/03/2026	Joan Ribas Serra	Draft 0.4: Revisions and Annex materials
0.5	23/03/2026	Christian Reynolds	Internal Review
0.6	26/03/2026	Andrea Borghini	Internal Review
0.7	30/03/2026	Maxime Michaud	Internal Review
0.8	30/03/2026	Joan Ribas Serra	Final Draft: Revisions and formatting
0.9	31/03/2026	Janita Van Dyk	Formatting and conclusion restructuring
0.9	31/03/2026	H. Rosi Song	Coordinator Approved
1.0	31/03/2026	H. Rosi Song	Final Submission

Abbreviations and acronyms

TERM	DEFINITION	TERM	DEFINITION
D[No.]	Deliverable [No.]	UCD	User-Centred Design
EC	European Commission	WP[No.]	Work Package [No.]
T[No.]	Task [No.]		

Consortium

ROLE	NAME	SHORT NAME	COUNTRY
Coordinator	University of Durham	UDUR	UK
Partner	Atlantic Technological University	ATU	Ireland
Partner	Barcelona Supercomputing Center	BSC	Spain
Partner	City, University of London	CITY	UK
Partner	Fundació Alícia	FA	Spain
Partner	Institut LYFE	LYFE	France
Partner	Instituto Superior Técnico	IST	Portugal
Partner	Roskilde University	RUC	Denmark
Partner	University College Cork	UCC	Ireland
Partner	University of Alicante	UA	Spain
Partner	University of Gastronomic Sciences of Pollenzo	UNISG	Italy
Partner	University of Milan	UMIL	Italy
Partner	University of Toronto	UoT	Canada

Legal disclaimer

RELISH is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101177427. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Contents

D3.2 Overview	i
Document history	i
Abbreviations and acronyms	ii
Consortium	ii
Legal disclaimer	ii
Contents	iii
List of Figures	iv
List of Tables	iv
Executive Summary	v
1 Introduction	5
1.1 Description of the document	5
1.2 Rationale	2
1.3 Survey overview and exclusions	3
2 Dataset Description and Use	3
2.1 Data transfer to consortium partners	5
3 Data Collection Methodology	6
3.1 Survey 1: Food & Culture Questionnaire (on youth food culture and cooking habits)	6
3.2 Review of studies and key findings	7
3.3 Reflections and decision-making	10
3.4 Survey 2: Futures Survey <i>and</i> Survey 3: Food Visions / Images (about the Future)	13
4 Survey Interface	16
4.1 Survey rationale	16
4.2 At-a-glance	17
5 Metadata and Variables	18
5.1 Survey 1: Food & Culture Questionnaire	18
5.2 Survey 2: Futures Survey <i>and</i> Survey 3: Food Visions / Images	19
6 Research Ethics and Data Management	21
6.1 Ethics protocols	22
6.2 Recruitment	23
7 Data Sample, Quality, and Limitations	24
7.1 Sample size	24
7.2 Current data quality	25
7.3 Anticipated limitations	25
7.4 Unanticipated limitations	26
8 Discussion	26
9 Conclusion	28
10 Bibliography	30
Annex I: Ethics Documentation	32
Annex II: Recruitment Materials	33
Annex III: Survey Questions	35
Annex IV: CSV Files	36

List of Figures

Figure 1: Screenshot of access links on relisheu.org/activities	13
Figure 2: Survey landing page (left) and information prompt (right) (mobile view)	18
Figure 3: Survey 1 sample section pages (mobile view)	19
Figure 4: Survey 2 sample questions and selection options (mobile view)	20
Figure 5: Survey 3 text-entry response section (desktop view)	21
Figure 6: Survey recruitment flyer	23
Figure 7: Instagram recruitment post (mobile view)	24

List of Tables

Table 1: Survey options and decisions breakdown.	10
--	----

Executive Summary

This document provides a précis and methodological overview for Deliverable 3.2 (D3.2), concerning data collected from surveys completed primarily by university students, carried out in partner institutions regarding emerging adults' culinary practices and knowledge, for use in the RELISH consortium.

This deliverable was primarily managed by Work Package 3 (FA), in collaboration with WP7 (IST) and WP9 (UA). Input on survey design and implementation was also provided by UNISG, UDUR, UMIL, and CITY.

1 Introduction

RELISH (Reframing European gastronomy Legacy through Innovation, Sustainability and Heritage) is a three-year Horizon Europe-funded project that offers a pathway to put into practice culinary recipes and food culture as cultural and digital tools to strengthen a crucial aspect of EU's common cultural heritage. Through an innovative and systematic approach to the understanding and use of traditional EU recipes via digital and AI-powered technology, it embarks on the production of a visual and verbal food storytelling web platform that aims to mediate social cohesion, reinforce EU cultural heritage transmission both at home and abroad through education and public engagement, while addressing sustainable practices in the home kitchen and the EU hospitality sector.

This deliverable was primarily managed by WP 3 (FA), in collaboration with WP7 (IST) and WP9 (UA), for the corresponding WP objective(s):

- To design a survey on the food practices of European youth to predict future European food and recipe scenarios.

1.1 Description of the document

This document provides a précis and methodological overview for D3.2, concerning data collected from surveys completed primarily by university students, carried out in partner institutions regarding emerging adults' culinary practices and knowledge, for use in the RELISH consortium.

To understand the potential interest of future generations in food heritage, WP3 and WP9 created three surveys on emerging adults' food perceptions and practices. We start from the conviction that, if we want to develop tools or create policies to promote culinary heritage aimed at the European population (especially young people), we must first understand their relationship with food (what they eat and why they eat it), and also their perception of the future. Only in this way can our understanding be as accurate as possible to provide knowledge that is useful for these generations. Also, for the tools that the project wants to create.

The surveys inform RELISH's broader objectives to develop tools and policies to promote culinary heritage for young people in Europe.

Drawing from **User-Centred Design** (UCD) for surveys, the responses generate a dataset and exploratory findings that inform the following RELISH WPs: WP4 (UMIL); WP7 & 8 (IST); and WP9 (UA).

The primary output for D3.2 comprises a current dataset (CSV) and corresponding of the survey results.

1.2 Rationale

The three surveys were designed around three data-gathering goals:

1. To broadly identify young people's present relationships and perceptions of food—what they eat, and why they eat it.
2. To broadly identify young people's perceptions of the future, and food practices and meanings' place in the future.
3. To enable real-time data for various WP mid-consortium reports and throughout the life of the project (2025–27).

Goal #3 also overlaps into platform design and development, providing access to living and cumulative data as respondents continue to enter information into survey platform (see links). An initial data collection period allowed us to offer a primary snapshot that will appear on the RELISH platform, but it can be updated each day by users who wish to contribute. The platform will create a collaborative space where everyday users can co-produce collective culinary identities and knowledge.

This material contributes to two major areas of the project:

- Providing the project partners with up-to-date data that can be analysed and used to support the development of future project tasks.
- Obtaining data to generate visualizations on the RELISH platform about the eating behaviour of Europeans.

Overall, these two data-gathering goals provide project partners with valuable information for future analysis. We cannot discuss or reflect on the value of cultural heritage without knowing the value that Europeans themselves assign to it. To keep culinary heritage alive and ensure that it is used by Europeans, we must understand the role it plays in their lives and how they imagine it will be in the future.

1.3 Survey overview and exclusions

The survey does not request data from those under 18 years of age and benefits from a greater sample of respondents aged 18–28 years. There are no exclusions based on country of origin, but the survey requires that respondents identify if they have lived in a European country for 3 or more months.

The sample is exploratory and not statistically representative: 50–100 responses are needed for initial analysis, with a desired of 500 responses per survey by the end of the project. Initial responses in the first round of data collection will be used for preliminary analysis. The survey is not intended to support generalization emerging adult perceptions and behaviours in European countries. The remaining responses gathered until the end of the project will maximize our understanding of the current and future perceptions of food landscapes.

Supplementary qualitative and quantitative data gathering in RELISH activities (through which additional ethics protocols will be created or amended) will be conducted to follow up on potential trends, comparisons, and correlations found in these surveys.

2 Dataset Description and Use

A brief description of the dataset is included, along with details of which project partners will use it and why.

GENERAL DATASET OVERVIEW

Dataset Name	Survey 1: Food & Culture Questionnaire Survey 2: Futures Survey Survey 3: Food Visions / Images (about the Future)
Type of data	Survey Results (multiple choice responses and plain-text entries)
Data collection period	December 2025 to March 2026 (First stage)
Target geographic coverage	Spain, Italy, France, United Kingdom, Ireland, Denmark, Portugal
Key questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• General (non-personally identifiable) demographic data (gender, age range, area of current residence, and socioeconomic background).• Perceptions and behaviours related to purchasing or making foods, including everyday meals and “typical” dishes from European cuisines.• Perceptions and values about the future of these foods and broader food systems changes that they might face.
Scales used	Closed questions Open-ended questions Frequency Degree of agreement (Likert scale)
Completion time	Survey 1: 10 min Survey 2: 5 min Survey 3: 20 min

Data collection began at the end of December 2025 and took place most intensively January to March 2026. The survey applications used for data collection will remain open for at least the entire duration of the project.

Three surveys were conducted:

- **Survey 1:** Food & Culture Questionnaire
- **Survey 2:** Futures Survey

- **Survey 3: Food Visions / Images (about the Future)**

Initially, only one survey was planned—Survey 1—with the aim of obtaining a contemporary snapshot of young people’s eating behaviours.

However, at the request of the WP9, two additional surveys were created, Surveys 2 and 3, focusing on collecting data related to the future of food. The overall objective became focussed not only on capturing an image of the present, but to also gather opinions and visions about the future of food, thus enabling work with future scenarios imagined by the participants.

The work carried out with the Food Memories thematic group in WP3 (Task 3.5), the youth surveys (Task 3.2) with the addition of the future-oriented surveys are meant to be complementary. They provide user-informed perspectives and relationships between the past, present, and future that help to furnish speculative future scenarios, enabling European culinary heritage to anticipate developments and position itself as a significant source of value.

Regarding the geographical coverage of the surveys, the initial intention was to collect data from the countries of the project partners: Spain, Italy, France, the United Kingdom, Ireland, Denmark, and Portugal. However, anyone is free to complete the questionnaires, regardless of their country of current residence or birth. The decision about which data will ultimately be used will be made at the stage of analysis and data visualisation.

2.1 Data transfer to consortium partners

The raw data collected through the surveys are transferred to other WPs. Data use responds to different WP objectives and will be analysed according to the interests and needs of the various phases of the project. The following section details which WPs receive the data and the current purposes for which they will be used:

- **WP4 – PREPPING:** The survey results are transferred to UMIL in WP4 for further analysis. The main objective is to provide WP4 with data on the current dietary behaviours of the sample, as well as participants’ perceptions and narratives about the future. This will support the analysis and understanding of the current relationship that citizens have with food and culinary heritage, allowing the proposed theoretical and ontological frameworks and tools to be better aligned with the reality described by the participants.

- **WP7 – SIMMERING:** The survey data are transferred to IST in WP7 to work on their visualisation and accessibility within the RELISH Platform. Survey 1 will inform their digital tool design within T7.6, Use-case #5: “Participatory design with young adults.” The aim is to operationalise insights to design an accessible and interactive visualisation intended for a broad audience, with the broader goal of encouraging reflection on the relationship between the value of tradition and contemporary food behaviours. At the same time, it seeks to promote behavioural change regarding the perception of the value of culinary heritage in European residents’ daily lives.
- **WP9 – PLATING:** All surveys, but especially those related to the future, will be transferred to UA in WP9 to support the development of future scenarios. The main objective is to explore, in a speculative way and based on participants’ perceptions, possible future scenarios concerning the relationship between culinary heritage, value, social behaviour, and future perspectives.

3 Data Collection Methodology

This section includes the literature review that informed the design of the three surveys, as well as the insights gained and the decisions made regarding the design.

3.1 Survey 1: Food & Culture Questionnaire (on youth food culture and cooking habits)

For the design of Survey 1, we considered both survey models and studies conducted by FA in recent years, as well as those developed by other institutions or research groups focused on data collection and the interpretation of dietary behaviour for various demographics populations.

This is not intended to be an exhaustive sample of the literature or survey formats, but rather a selection that allowed us to reflect on the type, number, and complexity of the questions we needed to ask, how participants should be recruited, which platforms should be used for data collection, and what the characteristics of the sample we aimed to consider should be.

We selected the following studies to review:

- *Internal Report* – Cuina per joves Project, funded by the Autonomous Government of Catalonia (Fundació Alícia 2024)

- *Featured Report* – “Cookpad: A Global Analysis of Cooking Around the World” (Gallup and Cookpad 2022)
- *Research Article* – “Culinary habits, nutritional knowledge, and healthy eating practices: A sociodemographic analysis of the Spanish population” (Sandri 2025)
- *Research Article* – “The Food Identity of Countries Differs Between Younger and Older Generations: A Cross-Sectional Study in American, European and Asian Countries” (Frez-Muñoz et al. 2021)
- *Research Article (ES/EN versions)* – “Barreras a la preparación de alimentos en casa y a la alimentación saludable entre los universitarios de Cataluña” (2023) / Barriers to Home Food Preparation and Healthy Eating among University Students in Catalonia (Jurado-Gonzalez et al. 2024)
- *Research Article* – “Strategies to Promote Healthy Eating among University Students: A Qualitative Study Using the Nominal Group Technique” (Wongprawmas et al. 2022)
- *Research Article* – “‘It’s Important but, on What Level?’: Healthy Cooking Meanings and Barriers to Healthy Eating among University Students” (Vélez-Toral et al. 2020).

3.2 Review of studies and key findings

Fundació Alícia (2024): “Cuina per joves,” Internal Report.

Research Institution / Location: Fundació Alícia, Spain

In this case, the commission from the regional government aimed to understand young people’s relationship with food and cooking to assess their skills and determine the best ways to help improve their culinary abilities. An initial focus group was conducted to explore their relationship with food and cooking. Based on the preliminary results, a survey was then developed using Google Forms and distributed through WhatsApp groups. To process the data and provide a preliminary analysis, specialised personnel were contracted. Sample size: n=565. Target age range: 12–35.

Gallup and Cookpad (2022): “A Global Analysis of Cooking Around the World,”
Featured Report. <https://www.gallup.com/analytics/512897/global-cooking-research.aspx>

Research Institution / Location: USA; private enterprise.

This survey was conducted for the culinary content platform Cookpad and had a global scope. It is a relatively simple survey, structured around two types of data. The first consists of general variables such as gender, region, employment status, household size, marital status, age, urbanicity, income quintile, education, subjective income, and parents. Sample size: n= more than 140 countries, but they do not state the total number of responses. Target age range: aged 15 and over.

The second type of data related to food, and is relatively concise, consisting of six questions on the topic allowing for different types of cross-analysis. The questions focus on meals and dinners prepared at home, including the frequency of eating and cooking and the person responsible for cooking. As the survey is conducted annually, it allows for generating longitudinal data over time. Data are collected from users of the Cookpad platform, and data processing was carried out by a specialised company.

Elena Sandri (2025): “Culinary habits, nutritional knowledge, and healthy eating practices: A sociodemographic analysis of the Spanish population,” *International Journal of Gastronomy and Food Science*, volume 40.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijgfs.2025.101185>

Research Institution / Location: Catholic University of Valencia, Spain

This survey was conducted with Spanish residents aged 18 and over. It combines sociodemographic variables with a set of nine questions related to culinary habits. The survey was implemented using Google Forms and distributed through social media. The researchers also contacted influencers via Instagram to promote the survey, as well as students from the Nutrition and Dietetics degree programme at the university conducting the study. Sample size: n=1534. Target age range: aged 18 and over.

Lucía Frez-Muñoz, Jarl K. Kampen, Vincenzo Fogliano, and Bea L P A Steenbekkers (2021): “The Food Identity of Countries Differs Between Younger and Older Generations: A Cross-Sectional Study in American, European and Asian Countries,” *Frontiers in Nutrition*, volume 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2021.653039>

Research Institution / Location: Wageningen University, the Netherlands

This study compares results between younger and older generations across different countries. Premising that traditional foods and beverages form a part of people's identities, it examines how mass media and migration flows may influence lifestyles and potentially transform food identity.

The main research tool used was a survey divided into two sections: a set of sociodemographic questions and another section focused on the specific interests of the project. These included tasks such as listing dishes, classifying them into categories, and identifying moments of consumption. The survey was implemented using Qualtrics, distributed via social media, and paid participant recruitment. A pilot survey was first conducted, and then questions were adjusted based on the preliminary results. Sample size: n=1784. Target age range: aged 18 and over.

Patricia Jurado-Gonzalez, F. Xavier Medina, and Anna Bach-Faig (2024): "Barriers to Home Food Preparation and Healthy Eating among University Students in Catalonia," *Appetite*, volume 194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2023.107159>

Research Institution / Location: Open University of Catalonia, Spain

This is a qualitative study in which focus groups were chosen as the main research method. A total of six focus groups were conducted. The conversations were structured around pre-selected themes such as perceptions of healthy habits, dietary changes during the university stage, and barriers to cooking and eating healthily at home. The sample was composed of university students in Catalonia, Spain. The discussions were transcribed and analysed using specialised qualitative analysis software. Sample size: n=24. Target age range 18 to 22.

Rungsaran Wongprawmas, Giovanni Sogari, Davide Menozzi, and Cristina Mora (2022): "Strategies to Promote Healthy Eating among University Students: A Qualitative Study Using the Nominal Group Technique," *Frontiers in Nutrition*, volume 9. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35187039/>

Research Institution / Location: University of Parma, Italy

A qualitative methodology was used in this study. The main research tool was the Nominal Group Technique. A total of 39 university students were recruited through announcements distributed across the university campus. The aim of the study was to understand dietary changes during the university period and the reasons behind them. Seven sessions were conducted with groups of 3–8 participants. The sessions involved structured questionnaires containing guided activities carried out individually to

gather information. The results were later transcribed and collated on Microsoft Excel for subsequent data extraction and analysis. Sample size: n=39. Target age range 19–26.

Mercedes Vélez-Toral, Carmen Rodríguez-Reinado, Ana Ramallo-Espinosa, and Montserrat Andrés-Villas (2020): “It’s Important but, on What Level?”: Healthy Cooking Meanings and Barriers to Healthy Eating among University Students,” *Nutrients*, volume 12, no. 8. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7468761/>

Research Institution / Location: University of Huelva, Spain

This study aimed to understand the type of diets followed by university students and the barriers they face when trying to maintain a healthy diet. The study was qualitative and based on focus group discussions. Selection criteria were established to define the sample. Participants were recruited through digital platforms commonly used by students and linked to the university. The focus groups were conducted through semi-structured discussions. During the sessions, short surveys were also used to collect more systematic information. The sessions were recorded and transcribed and later analysed using a content analysis method. Sample size: n=26. Target age range 19 to 30.

3.3 Reflections and decision-making

From the review of the literature, we identified several ideas and conclusions that were useful for the design and implementation of our survey, synthesised below and summarised.

Table 1: Survey options and decisions breakdown.

SURVEY TASK	OPTIONS	DECISION
A) Design & Pre-testing	Focus groups; pilot surveys; participant feedback	Initial focus group for survey question testing and revision
B) Survey Length (Question Number)	Short (10–15 questions, 5–10 min): highest recruitment, general data; Medium (15–30 questions, 10–15 min): high recruitment, targeted data; Long (30+ questions, 15–30min): lower recruitment, general and targeted data	Long survey, split into 3 surveys, achieving quality, depth, and cross-sectional data
C) Data Type	Sociodemographic; thematic	Two sections: socio-demographic and thematic; corresponding sub-sections

SURVEY TASK	OPTIONS	DECISION
D) Recruitment	Institutional; professional; paid; public; targeted (social media); snowballing	Combination of partner organisation and professional networks; broad social media; paid participation via the Prolific platform
E) Interface and Data Output	Platform: Google Forms, Qualtrics, fit-for-purpose; Data Output: CSV, fixed or continuous data collection format	Fit-for-purpose web app designed; fixed data collection CSV file with continuous collection and visualisation in development

A) DESIGN AND PRE-TESTING

In some cases, focus groups or preliminary survey drafts are conducted to better refine the final research instrument. Focus groups help identify relevant themes or even potential issues that need to be addressed. Preliminary surveys, on the other hand, make it possible to assess whether the questions are understandable, repetitive, or lack relevance.

Decision taken:

In our case, an initial focus group with young people was conducted (22/06/2025) to explore their relationship with food. This allowed us to create a list of questions that were later tested in a second focus group. This process enabled the development of a more accurate final questionnaire.

B) NUMBER OF QUESTIONS

Some studies that use surveys as their main research tool opt for a reduced number of questions. In principle, this reduces the time required to complete the survey and simplifies subsequent analysis, as it involves working with a smaller dataset.

Decision taken:

The possibility of designing a survey with a limited number of carefully selected questions was considered. However, the final decision was to develop a broader questionnaire with targeted or limited recruitment to collect quality and detailed cross-sectional data. For the subsequent analysis, it was considered that, if necessary, specific questions could be selected based on their relevance according to the responses obtained.

C) TYPE OF DATA COLLECTED

All studies that use surveys as a research tool tend to divide the data into two main sections: sociodemographic data and thematic data directly related to the object of study.

Decision taken:

We maintained this type of segmentation. The combination of sociodemographic data with questions related to food allows for greater analytical and comparative analyses and makes it possible to consider variables from a sociological perspective. Thematic sections were further organized in sub-sections to provide clarity and structure.

D) RECRUITMENT STRATEGIES AND CHANNELS

This issue is one of the most controversial, due to the difficulty of accessing a sufficiently significant sample of participants. Increasingly, social media appear to be effective channels for recruiting participants, when direct recruitment to them is not available. On the other hand, studies linked to universities often rely on their own students, requiring obtaining often lengthy ethical protocol approvals. In some cases, paying participants for their responses is also considered as a possible strategy.

Decision taken:

Since the consortium includes educational institutions, it was considered appropriate to distribute the survey among the students of these institutions. Graphic materials providing access to the survey were created, and the survey was also disseminated publicly through RELISH social media platforms, individual member accounts, on the RELISH website (see **Figure 1**), teaching and research colleagues, and professional and academic association email listservs. As a back-up to increase sample size, we had the capacity to recruit a small number of paid participants through the Prolific survey platform.

E) DATA REPOSITORY

Beyond deciding where the data will be hosted while ensuring privacy and restricted access to participants' information, another important issue concerns how data are stored. Once the information has been collected, it can be downloaded and used in

different software tools that facilitate its analysis. Having data available in Excel (CSV) files appears to be particularly useful, as it allows for flexible manipulation and analysis.

Decision taken:

A dedicated web/mobile survey application was developed by IST Partner to maintain full control over the data and prevent its use by third parties. Through this application, it is possible to visualise individual responses as well as aggregated results. The system also allows download of survey responses as a CSV file, enabling the results to be stored in shared RELISH servers that can be consulted and manipulated. The survey application will remain active at least for the duration of the project to continue collecting responses. The data are updated in real time, allowing continuous monitoring of incoming responses.

Figure 1: Screenshot of access links on relish.eu.org/activities

3.4 Survey 2: Futures Survey and Survey 3: Food Visions / Images (about the Future)

The methodological design adopted in this research responds to a sequential and complementary mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative techniques. The surveys aim to capture both the structuring of social perceptions and

the symbolic construction of the future by young people. This approach is aligned with contemporary participatory foresight frameworks, which emphasise the importance of gathering different types of evidence to strengthen both the analytical validity and the interpretative capacity of future-oriented analysis (Rosa, Warnke, and Gemünden 2021).

First, UA developed a structured survey on perceptions of the future, based on even-numbered Likert-type scales. The choice of scales without a midpoint responds to the need to avoid neutral responses that may conceal latent attitudes, poorly defined positions, or forms of evasion when addressing evaluative questions. This type of design is particularly relevant in foresight studies, where the objective is not limited to recording opinions, but rather to identify orientations, expectations, and emerging social tensions.

Furthermore, the questionnaire was designed according to methodological rigour criteria:

- The order of questions follows a logical sequence that reduces carryover bias and priming effects.
- The inclusion of control questions allows for verifying the internal consistency of responses.
- The organization into differentiated blocks—sociodemographic, socioeconomic, and perceptions of the future—facilitates multivariable analysis and social segmentation.
- Item wording was carefully crafted to avoid semantic ambiguities and to enhance the comparability of results.

Second, UA incorporated a qualitative narrative questionnaire, aimed at exploring social representations of the future from a discursive perspective. This technique makes it possible to capture not only what subjects think, but how they imagine, articulate, and narrate their future, thus accessing symbolic, emotional, and cultural dimensions that cannot be captured through closed-ended instruments. In this sense, the narrative approach is not conceived as a secondary complement, but rather as an appropriate methodological tool for gathering imaginaries, frameworks of meaning, and ways of interpreting change.

The combination of both tools is complementary: while the survey allows for identifying structured and comparable patterns, storytelling provides interpretative depth and enhances the understanding of the cultural frameworks within which

these perceptions are embedded. This articulation between measurement and interpretation is consistent with partners' prior research literature on participatory foresight (see for example Bas 2002; 2004; 2014; Bas and Guilló 2012; Guilló 2014), in which studying the future requires integrating cognitive, normative, and experiential dimensions rather than reducing it to a single data collection instrument.

The choice of these tools is also grounded in methodologies previously applied in foresight research within corresponding partners' institutional contexts. In particular, the survey on perceptions of the future is linked to the completed project **Fahrenheit 212 – Creative Futures & Innovative Ideas (F212)**,¹ funded by the Fundación Española para la Ciencia y la Tecnología (FECYT).

From a methodological standpoint, F212's relevance lies in its orientation toward analysing **images of the future**, understood as **constructs that integrate expectations, values, and social representations**. The F212 methodology, presented in Guilló (2013), used social platforms and participatory foresight tools to assess images of the future among young people. Similarly, UA and IST structured survey instruments into comparable thematic blocks—economy, culture, politics, among others—to systematically collect attitudes and visions of the future suitable for comparative analysis.

Additionally, the narrative questionnaire relates to **Stories from 2050**,² developed within the framework of the European Commission and published by the Publications Office of the European Union (European Commission 2021). This project was structured as a participatory foresight exercise based on collecting stories constructed “from the future,” generated through an open platform in which young people and students mainly participated. These narratives were conceived as a qualitative corpus aimed at exploring different representations of the future and analysing the potential of stories as tools for thinking about the future.

The methodological relevance of Stories from 2050 lies in how it legitimises storytelling as a research device in foresight: not for predictive purposes but rather for analytical ones. Narratives allow for integrating—within a single discourse—cognitive, normative, and experiential dimensions, facilitating analysis of social imaginaries, values, and frameworks for interpreting change. Therefore, stories' usefulness relates to their value in reconstructing how different social actors imagine, organize, and give meaning to the future in contexts of uncertainty.

¹ <https://futurlab.es/?p=261>

² <https://www.storiesfrom2050.com/>

Overall, combining structured surveys and narrative approaches is a complementary strategy already found in specialised literature and previously described institutional precedents. Survey 2 makes it possible to obtain systematic and comparable information on attitudes toward the future, while Survey 3’s narrative approach enables analysis of how these attitudes are articulated in discourses and imaginaries. This integration makes it possible to address **the future as an object of measurement and from its interpretative dimension**, in line with applied social foresight approaches developed in the European context (Bas and Guilló 2015).

Participatory foresight has become one of the most relevant methodological approaches within applied futures studies. Rosa, Kimpeler, Schirrmeister, and Warnke (2021) argue that these approaches articulate plural visions, collective learning processes, and strategy-building within mission-oriented innovation frameworks. Similarly, a systematic review by Barendregt, Kloet, and Vervoort (2024) shows that public participation in “futuring” processes broadens the diversity of perspectives and enhances the democratic potential of anticipatory processes.

In the European context, **the EC has progressively adopted participatory foresight**, which links strategic foresight with participatory and long-term forms of governance. The **2020 Strategic Foresight Report** (European Commission 2020) states that strategic foresight should promote participatory, future-oriented governance in dialogue with institutions, member states, experts, and citizens. Within this framework, participatory foresight gains relevance for European projects, as it includes non-expert actors—including young people—in knowledge production useful for transition, resilience, and innovation policies.

4 Survey Interface

With consultation from FA, UA, and UDUR, IST developed a survey web application, to collect survey responses prior to circulation. The application was designed, revised, and finalised in November 2025.

4.1 Survey rationale

Developing a “fit-for-purpose” survey application allowed safe and secure data collection and management inaccessible to third parties (*e.g.*, compared to Google Forms) and flexibility in organising and displaying research-related activities.

Additional considerations also included:

- User-Experience / User-Interface (UX/UI) for target users (emerging adults), especially optimised for mobile devices (phone or tablet)
- Enabling real-time data gathering and visualisations (in development)
- Flexibility for updating surveys, hosting complementary or future RELISH surveys, and incorporating RELISH's visual identity
- Future interoperability with other digital RELISH platforms and tools
- Potential pathways for survey application development or licensing for external academic or community research projects

4.2 At-a-glance

Participants were provided with three links via relevant recruitment channels. The links take participants to a separate website portal for the corresponding survey.

The first page of each survey includes a brief description of the relevant survey, project information, purpose of data gathering activity, and general contact information.

A selection area on the Home page, “**Hide Information**” / “**Show Information,**” creates a dropdown section with Informed Consent checkbox procedure, organised and written in plain, accessible language (see **Figure 2**).

Participants click through each page until they have completed all the required entries.

Participants have the option to provide personal or professional email contact information in the application, which is extracted and secured confidentially from the survey result data. This information was collected so that RELISH partners can follow up directly with participants regarding developments, research findings, and first access to visualisations or publications.

Figure 2: Survey landing page (left) and information prompt (right) (mobile view)

5 Metadata and Variables

This section describes the organisation, metadata, and variables corresponding to each survey. The full list of questions and question type (scale units, nominal scale units, plain text-entry) for each survey can be found in **Annex III**.

5.1 Survey 1: Food & Culture Questionnaire

This survey is organized into four sections. The first section collects a set of sociodemographic data. The following three sections address participants' relationships with food. In total, there are 60 questions:

- Section 1: *About You. Let's start with a quick snapshot of who you are*
- Section 2: *Exploring your connection with food*
- Section 3: *Let's explore the flavours and traditions that define your food world*
- Section 4: *Your Cooking Style. Let's get a taste of how you work in the kitchen*

The questions combine closed and open-ended responses. In some cases, there are combined questions. Depending on the participant's answer, they may be given the option to continue responding to additional questions; otherwise, they proceed to the next one. For closed questions, two types of measurement units are used: scale units and nominal scale units.

Figure 3: Survey 1 sample section pages (mobile view)

5.2 Survey 2: Futures Survey and Survey 3: Food Visions / Images

Survey 2 includes 17 questions, all of which are closed-ended. They are presented consecutively, but the data collected are divided into two sections.

The first questions are sociodemographic and measured using nominal scale units.

The remaining questions relate to perceptions of the future from a geographical perspective—at the level of the world, Europe, or the respondent's country of residence—and address major social topics as: Economy, Politics, Culture, the Ecosystem, Security, and Technology. These are measured using scale units.

Figure 4: Survey 2 sample questions and selection options (mobile view)

Survey 3 begins with a first group of questions of a sociodemographic nature. These are closed-ended and measured using nominal scale units.

The second group of questions is open-ended and more qualitative and/or narrative in nature. Participants are asked to respond to a single prompt: “A Day in life in 2050.” Respondents were asked to imagine that they are living in 2050 and write a short free essay, story, or diary entry about a day in their life, focusing on how they cook or eat.

Figure 5: Survey 3 text-entry response section (desktop view)

6 Research Ethics and Data Management

No personal identifying information (names, addresses, correspondence) is collected, unless a participant voluntarily provides their email to request that RELISH follow-up with them on project updates and their data use.

All data collected on the digital application is first stored on a physical, password-protected server in a locked location at IST. Correspondence information is extracted from survey responses and securely stored and protected in a separate database on our servers.

Compiled data is regularly updated and shared with all RELISH consortium partners according to the RELISH Data Management Protocol (DMP), in accordance with Horizon Europe protocols. A curated version of this dataset will be copied from IST's servers to Zenodo, an internationally reputable database for securely storing data for public access and citation purposes.

This curated dataset will be held in Zenodo for an additional 5 years after the project concludes to generate research and conform to the project's funding agreement with the European Commission (via Horizon Europe). After 5 years, project partners can

choose to store a copy of data on an encrypted folder in perpetuity to generate future research. This data will be deleted from Zenodo after this 5-year period.

Participants have the option to share their name and correspondence details if they would like to have updates about the use of their data and future RELISH activities or participation. Survey organizers' names and emails are shared with all participants for any questions or concerns about the survey or digital application.

6.1 Ethics protocols

Survey design and data collection partners completed and received approval for institutional research ethics with human participants protocols. Other partners intending to engage in survey recruitment from their respective institutions also completed ethics approvals at their corresponding institution.

A multi-institutional Survey Ethics Justification document was created to append to individual ethics protocols (see **Annex I**) to facilitate consistent language and content, as well as clarify multi-institutional management for ethics committees.

The following institutions completed and received approval for research ethics protocols pertaining to the surveys:

- Fundació Alícia
- University of Alicante
- Durham University
- City, University of London
- University of Gastronomic Sciences
- Atlantic Technological University
- Roskilde University

The Ethics Protocols were defined as: low-risk and exploratory, with confidential and anonymised data participation procedures.

6.2 Recruitment

Ethics protocols covered institutional and non-institutional recruitment channels (e.g., social media, professional networks and colleagues). Recruitment materials and strategies were stored and shared on RELISH's Teams channel, including:

- Standard email boilerplate template (see **Annex II**) for professional colleague or association listservs
- PDF flyer for print or digital circulation (see **Figure 6** and **Annex II**)
- Social media PNGs for Instagram.

Figure 6: Survey recruitment flyer

Recruitment posts were circulated on Instagram once every month in Instagram Stories between December and March 2026 and shared on RELISH's LinkedIn account.

Figure 7: Instagram recruitment post (mobile view)

7 Data Sample, Quality, and Limitations

This section discusses, based on the first stage, the data sample, its current quality, and preliminary limitations as of March 2026.

The data is stored within our application and can be downloaded as CSV files (see **Annex IV**).

7.1 Sample size

As of **March 31, 2026**, we have collected the following number of responses per survey. For preliminary analysis, we estimated that a minimum sample of 50–100 responses would be sufficient.

Survey 1	467 responses
Survey 2	181 responses
Survey 3	140 responses
TOTAL	788 responses

For each survey, we exceeded our anticipated sample size. We anticipate that this sample size will grow further, as the surveys will continue to be open for responses until the end of 2027.

7.2 Current data quality

Participants responded to the surveys voluntarily, which suggests that there was no motivation to answer the questions inaccurately. In this sense, the data can be considered indicative, with limitations.

However, this is different in the case of open-ended questions that require participants to write their own responses, introducing inconsistency and variability. These types of questions can generate issues when calculating the final responses and percentages. For example, when respondents are asked to indicate their favourite dish, a sequence of answers might be pasta, spaghetti, spaghetti carbonara, lasagna, macaroni. In numerical terms, these responses would initially be counted as 2, 1, 1, 1, 1. Although they would be recorded separately, they all belong to the same broader category of “pasta dishes”, which in practice would represent a total count of 6. This requires data cleaning.

Manual automated categorization can be done by creating a dictionary of keywords for each category. For example, “pasta dishes” could include [“pasta”, “spaghetti”, “lasagna”, “macaroni”, “ravioli”], and “pizza” could include [“pizza”, “margherita”, “pepperoni”]. Then, a script in Python, Excel, or R can be used to assign each response to its corresponding category. This approach allows for a more “mechanical” grouping of responses without manually reviewing each row. Or Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques can be applied to automatically group open-ended survey responses by analysing the meaning and similarity of the text.

7.3 Anticipated limitations

The survey has only been made available in the following language: **English**. This limitation was imposed to allow for non-ambiguous comparisons between responses and to avoid potential multiple meanings produced by multiple language translations.

While the survey aims to gather responses from a wide range of geographic and socio-economic backgrounds in Europe, we anticipated that responses from participants with middle-class backgrounds and those enrolled in **higher-education institutions** in countries where partners are affiliated would comprise the sampled majority. The current sample reflects this.

In terms of geographical distribution, a larger proportion of responses come from **Spain**, which likely reflects the RELISH institutional sample (2 institutions recruiting in Spain).

Although most responses fall within the expected age group (emerging adults), demonstrating our targeted recruitment strategies were successful, the values for the remaining age groups are not as proportionate, which may require us to exclude them from subsequent data analysis. Toward the end of the project when a larger sample is available, more proportionate representation across age groups would enable comparative analysis at a later stage.

7.4 Unanticipated limitations

Based on the data collected so far, we observed some preliminary limitations in terms of the balance of the sample.

Regarding gender, thus far there is a higher number of responses from respondents who self-selected “**female**.” This may reflect higher education demographics or perhaps also the topic of the survey, and merits further analysis.

8 Discussion

In this first preliminary analysis, we focus on Surveys 1 and 2. Survey 3, as it provides qualitative data, requires more time to process and analyse.

Regarding **Survey 1**, it was decided to make it open to all age groups. The sampling and recruitment strategies were successful, with most responses come from participants in the 18–25 age range.

Uploading the survey to the **Prolific** platform (which offers financial compensation), allowed greater sample balance for geographic region and age group. However, responses need to be reviewed to ensure validity, and may affect results. The data obtained will be cleaned to better assess the actual situation of this age group. Initial review suggests that the results have not changed significantly from pre-Prolific sample.

Approximately half of current participants (Survey 1, n=225 [50%]) have had an experience abroad. To a greater or lesser extent, respondents identified that this changed their eating habits. However, the destination country does not necessarily

correspond to the cuisine participants ultimately value. So far, the sample shows that the most visited country is Spain (Survey 1, n=44 [9.8%]), but the cuisine people feel most connected to is Italian (Survey 1, n=277 [61.5%]), which does not necessarily imply that they have lived in Italy.

From the six cuisines represented in the survey, participants felt most connected to only two European ones—Italian and, at a much lower level, Spanish. The category “other” appears in fourth place (this includes a wide range of regional European cuisines, as well as Northern and Eastern European cuisines and others from around the world). However, when considered separately, none of these enter the top 10.

Participants’ connection to Italian cuisine preliminarily correlates with the food participants report eating regularly. Pasta and pizza are the most frequently mentioned (Survey 1, n=147 [32.6%]). The central role of these foods or dishes is further stressed when comparing to question responses on what they would eat if they could choose only one dish (the “dish on a desert island” question). While there is some diversity of dishes in both questions, preliminary interpretation suggests that there are three dominant categories of central dishes in this order: pasta, pizza, and rice (Survey 1, n=50, 35, 20).

The majority of participants indicated preferences for home-cooked food (Survey 1, n=374 [83.1%]) and traditional family recipes (Survey 1, n=225 (50%)). Preferences for international and fusion cuisine (Survey 1, n=155 [34,44%]) was a significant minority. In a question on defining one’s food culture, participant responses thematically suggest many describe their food culture as a mix of influences, even though they also value family heritage. At first glance, this suggests a tendency toward an ambiguous behaviour between tradition and modern food culture. Nevertheless, participants commonly identified their culinary style as traditional and home-based (Survey 1, n=215 [47.7%]).

Participants were asked to identify several iconic dishes. The majority of participants indicated they cooked these dishes more often for others than for themselves. For the most part, the iconic dishes identified correspond to what participants consider they currently eat. However, when they do not often or ever eat an identified iconic dish, it is either because the participants prefer other types of food (Survey 1, n=57 [12.6%]) or because these dishes take too long to prepare (Survey 1, n=54 [12%]).

An additional relevant preliminary theme concerns food provisioning and management. Based on current responses, price, pleasure, and health remain central factors in decision-making when buying and eating food (Survey 1, n= 285 [63.3%]). Almost all participants reported shopping at supermarkets (Survey 1, n=427 [94.8%]), with a much smaller proportion using small traditional shops (Survey 1, n=197

[43.7%]) or markets (Survey 1, n=124 [27.5%]). Online food shopping is still not widely reported in this age group (Survey 1, n=65 [14.4%]).

Many of these responses encourage further consideration of the role(s) that culinary heritage and traditional recipes play in Europe today. Further considerations also include the food environment people live in and how heritage and the recipes that compose it can be central to their lives.

Regarding **Survey 2**, most respondents were born between 2002 and 2006 (18-25 age range). Concerning current participants' perceptions of the future, more participants indicated that they feel relatively optimistic about their personal future, but that they are less optimistic about the future of the world, Europe, or their country. Another preliminary result is that while participants consider economy, politics, the ecosystem, security, and technology close to extremely relevant, responses to culture are less decisive.

Overall, current response data indicates that participants' perceptions of the future does not fall into extreme views: they are neither highly optimistic nor highly pessimistic, although there is a tendency toward negative thinking, in contrast with a more positive outlook on their own future.

9 Conclusion

This deliverable (D3.2) describes the design, methods, survey instruments, and preliminary findings associated with three surveys for young people working and studying in Europe related to their food practices, eating habits, and perceptions and images about the future.

The surveys are hosted on a fit-for-purpose survey platform designed by IST that supports live data visualisations and CSV files for public and research use. The survey platform will continue to collect responses until the end of the project's granting period.

Surveys 1 and 2 have undergone preliminary analysis by FA and UA. Survey 3 (long-form answers) will be qualitatively analysed by UA to develop future scenarios.

All survey data and findings will also be handed to UMIL, CITY, and UA for further analysis on youth food behaviours, meanings, sustainability implications, and developing future scenarios. Data and findings will also be used by IST to develop digital tool design.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

RELISH project partners thank survey participants for their time and effort responding to our surveys. Their responses greatly contribute to RELISH in providing novel data and understandings of young people's food practices, identities, and meanings.

10 Bibliography

- Barendregt, Laura, Roy Bendor, and Bregje F. van Eekelen. 2024. "Public Participation in Futuring: A Systematic Literature Review." *Futures* 158 (April): 103346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2024.103346>.
- Bas, Enric. 2002. *Prospectiva: Cómo usar el pensamiento sobre el futuro*. 1st ed. Ariel.
- Bas, Enric. 2004. *Megatendencias para el siglo XXI*. Un estudio Delfos. Fondo de Cultura Económica.
- Bas, Enric. 2014. "Educar para innovar: la innovación como cultura. Juventud, proactividad, creatividad, participación y visión de futuro compartida." *Revista de Estudios de Juventud*, Imágenes de futuro en la juventud, vol. 104: 11–30.
- Bas, Enric. 2016. "La prospectiva participativa en contexto. El Método FLUX-3D, una herramienta para la innovación social." In *El futuro a debate: Respuestas prospectivas y estratégicas ante la incertidumbre global*, edited by Tomás Miklos and Margarita Arroyo. Limusa.
- Bas, Enric, and Mario Guilló, eds. 2012. *Prospectiva e innovación*. Vol. 1: Visiones. Plaza y Valdés Editores.
- Bas, Enric, and Mario Guilló. 2015. "Participatory Foresight for Social Innovation. FLUX-3D Method (Forward Looking User Experience), a Tool for Evaluating Innovations." *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 101 (December): 275–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2015.06.016>.
- European Commission. 2020. *2020 Strategic Foresight Report: Charting the Course towards a More Resilient Europe*. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2873/58081>.
- European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation. 2021. *Stories from 2050: Radical, Inspiring and Thought Provoking Narratives around Challenges and Opportunities of Our Futures*. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/203724>.
- Frez-Muñoz, Lucía, Jarl K. Kampen, Vincenzo Fogliano, and Bea L. P. A. Steenbekkers. 2021. "The Food Identity of Countries Differs Between Younger and Older Generations: A Cross-Sectional Study in American, European and Asian Countries." *Frontiers in Nutrition* 8: 653039. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2021.653039>.
- Gallup, and Cookpad. 2022. *Cookpad: A Global Analysis of Cooking Around the World*. Gallup. <https://www.gallup.com/analytics/512897/global-cooking-research.aspx>.
- Guilló, Mario. 2013. "Futures, Communication and Social Innovation: Using Participatory Foresight and Social Media Platforms as Tools for Evaluating Images of the Future among Young People." *European Journal of Futures Research* 1 (17): 17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40309-013-0017-2>.
- Guilló, Mario. 2014. "Imágenes de futuro, prospectiva e innovación: explorando el potencial de las redes sociales para el desarrollo de procesos de innovación abierta entre jóvenes universitarios de España y Finlandia." *Revista de Estudios de Juventud*, Monográfico *Imágenes de futuro en la juventud*, vol. 104: 99–108.
- Jurado-Gonzalez, Patricia, F. Xavier Medina, and Anna Bach-Faig. 2024. "Barriers to Home Food Preparation and Healthy Eating among University Students in Catalonia." *Appetite* 194 (March): 107159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2023.107159>.
- Rosa, Aaron B., Simone Kimpeler, Elna Schirrmeister, and Philine Warnke. 2021. "Participatory Foresight and Reflexive Innovation: Setting Policy Goals and Developing Strategies in a Bottom-up,

Mission-Oriented, Sustainable Way." *European Journal of Futures Research* 9 (1): 2.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40309-021-00171-6>.

Sandri, Elena. 2025. "Culinary Habits, Nutritional Knowledge, and Healthy Eating Practices: A Sociodemographic Analysis of the Spanish Population." *International Journal of Gastronomy and Food Science* 40 (June): 101185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijgfs.2025.101185>.

Vélez-Toral, Mercedes, Carmen Rodríguez-Reinado, Ana Ramallo-Espinosa, and Montserrat Andrés-Villas. 2020. "'It's Important but, on What Level?': Healthy Cooking Meanings and Barriers to Healthy Eating among University Students." *Nutrients* 12 (8): 2309.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/nu12082309>.

Wongprawmas, Rungsaran, Giovanni Sogari, Davide Menozzi, and Cristina Mora. 2022. "Strategies to Promote Healthy Eating Among University Students: A Qualitative Study Using the Nominal Group Technique." *Frontiers in Nutrition* 9: 821016. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2022.821016>.

Annex I: Ethics Documentation

Annex I includes relevant documentation for cross-institutional Ethics Committees.

The primary document attached is the **“RELISH Survey Explanation and Justification for Partner Institutions.”**

RELISH Survey Explanation and Justification for Partner Institutions

1. Project and Work Package Overview

Participants will be asked to complete a two-part survey for **RELISH (Reframing European gastronomy Legacy through Innovation, Sustainability and Heritage)**. Funded by Horizon Europe (HORIZON-CL-2024_Heritage-01 call, Project No. 101177427), RELISH is composed of project partners from 12 participating institutions. RELISH seeks to understand how emerging adults negotiate changes to food and recipes associated with their home region or place of residence, and how these changes affect their sense of identity, memory, and social connection in European contexts. Drawing from these findings, RELISH will produce a digital platform to foster dynamic and inclusive engagement with meaningful food recipes, histories, and memories and provide guides and recommendations on supporting related sustainability and culinary innovations.

This survey is organized by Work Package 3: “Ingredients,” led by Dr. Joan Ribas (Fundació Alícia, in Barcelona, Spain), with contributions from FUTURLAB at the University of Alicante (Spain) and Durham University (UK), with technical support from the Instituto Superior Técnico at the University of Lisbon (Portugal).

Fundació Alícia (FA) is a private, non-profit foundation created in 2003, under the auspices of Fundació Catalunya La Pedrera. FA is a centre that researches culinary products and processes, innovating and working to improve people’s diets with a special focus on food restrictions, health, heritage, and sustainability.

FUTURLAB-Creative Futures is a special research unit at the University of Alicante. FUTURLAB engages in organisational training, knowledge transfer, basic and applied research and benchmarking. It uses a transversal/multidisciplinary approach for working with public institutions, private companies, and NGOs facing complexity and future uncertainty.

The survey’s design and management are conducted by experienced social science, humanities, and technical researchers and academics with familiarity in qualitative and quantitative survey design, samplings, and analysis from Spain, Portugal, Italy, and the UK.

2. Survey Design and Purpose

Participants will be asked to anonymously complete a survey with two parts, one composed of approximately 60 multiple-choice and short (several words or sentences) questions, and the second part is composed of 6 multiple-choice and 1 free writing essay question (no more than 3000 characters). Altogether, the survey should take no more than 35 min. The survey questions solicit responses on:

 @relish_he

RELISH: Reframing European gastronomy Legacy through Innovation, Sustainability, and Heritage

Project: 101177427 – RELISH – HORIZON-CL2-2024-HERITAGE-01

rosi.song@durham.ac.uk

relish.eu.org

- 1) General (non-personally identifiable) demographic data (gender, age range, area of current residence, and socioeconomic background);
- 2) Perceptions and behaviours related to purchasing or making foods, including everyday meals and “typical” dishes from European cuisines; and
- 3) Perceptions and values about the future of these foods and broader food systems changes that they might face.

Sampling: Requests for survey participation will be primarily distributed through RELISH-managed channels (e.g. social media and website), and higher education correspondence channels (e.g. listservs, university outreach, ERASMUS programs, and colleague word-of-mouth).

The survey will be housed and collect responses on a central RELISH-designed and managed web application using a local server.

This survey is exploratory. Convenience, purposive, and snow-balling sampling methods will be used.

The first round of responses (to achieve 50–100 responses) will be gathered in November and December 2025. The survey will be open for collecting responses until the end of the project’s granting period (December 2027).

Purpose: The primary purpose of the first survey part is to understand correlations between emerging adults’ perception on “typical” (heritage, regional, local, or broadly meaningful dishes associated with their identities) foods and their everyday food consumption behaviours (i.e. whether they eat, share, or value these dishes in their everyday life). Furthermore, the survey seeks to understand if experiences of mobility (e.g. study abroad or exchange programs, migrating for work, and longer stays in other countries they did not grow up in) and future outlooks impact their food perceptions and behaviours. The second part of the survey question will generate open-ended responses related to food and its connections to the anticipated future of culture, economy, sustainability, and politics in Europe.

The survey data will also allow for preliminary comparative analysis on regional, national, and socioeconomic differences between participants’ perceptions and behaviours.

Survey data will be used to create and/or supplement visualisations and interactive storytelling accessible to the public on the pilot RELISH platform. This platform will be a digital innovation gathering all RELISH activities into one centralized and dynamic hub for knowledge transmission and engagement on recipes, heritage and sustainability. Data may also be presented in synthesized, aggregated, and/or analysed forms in research publications and public updates on RELISH findings and activities.

3. Participation and Consent

The survey will be open to adult participants aged 18 years and older, with purposive sampling used when appropriate to gather responses for participants who are in typical higher-education and early-working age ranges (18–28 years of age). An open survey with purposive sampling will allow for greater sample response rate and potential generational comparisons on food perceptions.

Participants will be asked to complete this survey on a web application designed and run by RELISH partners. They will be advised on their right to consent to take or not take the survey, with no impact on their personal and professional standing. They will have access to future surveys available on this same web application (pending future ethics approvals or amendments).

The survey may be circulated by partners' professional colleagues or networks in classrooms or course communications. Depending on the institution or instructor, participants may expect compensation in-kind (e.g. extra-credit), but survey completion will never be made mandatory.

4. Limitations

The survey will only be made available in the following language: English. This limitation is imposed to allow for non-ambiguous comparisons between responses and to avoid potential multiple meanings produced by multiple language translations.

While the survey aims to gather responses from a wide range of geographic and socio-economic backgrounds in Europe, we anticipate that responses from participants with middle-class backgrounds and those enrolled in institutions in countries where partners are affiliated will comprise the sampled majority.

The survey is exploratory (no statistical relevance): 50–100 responses are needed for analysis, with a desired maximum of 500 responses. Initial responses in the first round of data collection will be used for preliminary analysis. This survey will not be applicable to generalising emerging adult perceptions and behaviours in European countries. The remaining responses gathered until the end of the project will maximise our understanding of the current and future perceptions of food landscapes.

Supplementary qualitative and quantitative data gathering in RELISH activities (through which additional ethics protocols will be created or amended) will be conducted to follow up on potential trends, comparisons, and correlations found in these surveys.

The survey will not request data from those under 18 years of age and benefits from a greater sample of respondents aged 18–28 years. There are no exclusions based on country of origin,

but the survey requires that respondents identify if they have lived in a European country for 3 or more months.

5. Data Confidentiality, Security and Handling

No personal identifying information (names, addresses, correspondence) will be collected, unless a participant voluntarily provides their name and email to request that RELISH follow-up with them on project updates and their data use. All data collected on the digital application will be first stored on a physical, password-protected server in a locked location at IST. Correspondence information will be automatically extracted from survey responses and securely stored and protected in a separate database on our servers.

Data will then be moved and shared with all RELISH consortium partners (institutions listed below) according to the RELISH Data Management Protocol (DMP), overseen by Horizon Europe. A curated version of this data will be copied from IST's servers to Zenodo, an internationally reputable database for securely storing data for public access and citation purposes.

This curated data will be held in Zenodo for an additional 5 years after the project concludes to generate research and conform to the project's funding agreement with the European Commission (via Horizon Europe). After 5 years, project partners can choose to store a copy of data on an encrypted folder in perpetuity to generate future research. This data will be deleted from Zenodo after this 5-year period.

6. Communication and Requests for Future Participation

Participants will have the option to share their name and correspondence details if they would like to have updates about the use of their data and future RELISH activities or participation. Survey organizers' names and emails (listed below) will be shared with all participants for any questions or concerns about the survey or digital application.

Survey participants will be made aware when deciding to complete the survey that they will have the option to participate in future RELISH surveys made available between 2026 and 2027 on this application, if eligible.

7. Risks and Benefits

This survey is low-risk and no harm to participants is reasonably anticipated—the surveys do not mandatorily request personally identifiable information, nor responses that could solicit potentially stressful or negative recollections or reflections. No deception will be employed.

Depending on how the survey information was circulated, participants may anticipate compensation in-kind (e.g. extra-credit on an assignment or course grade). If survey response

rates within the first two months do not meet the minimum threshold (100 responses), survey organisers will create an opt-in draw for respondents to win one of several €50 grocery gift cards.

Participants will receive updates about how their data was used in follow-up communications through a previously agreed communication channel (e.g., if they choose to share a correspondence email address).

Participants may derive emotional and/or social satisfaction from responding and reflecting on the information that the survey solicits, particularly on the relationships between changing identities, food practices and experiences of migration to or within Europe. They may derive a sense of positive ownership over how their responses feed into visualisations, digital storytelling and their future access to and/or participation in the RELISH platform.

8. Institutional Agreements and Funding

When required, consortium partners who are participating in the design, circulation, and use of collected survey data will be responsible for securing institutional research ethics protocols with human participants.

RELISH and its data gathering activities are funded by Horizon Europe (HE), under the call: HORIZON-CL2-2024-Heritage-01. Project information can be found on HE's Cordis database through the following link: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101177427> or Project No.: 101177427.

As an HE-funded project, RELISH conforms to "[The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#)" (European Commission, Revised Edition 2023), developed by the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities (ALLEA). The Code of Conduct outlines the principles, good research practices, and conditions of violating research integrity for all participating projects.

The RELISH project is coordinated by Durham University (UK) and led by Dr. H. Rosi Song (School of Modern Languages and Cultures).

The participating institutions are:

- Fundació Alcía (Spain)
- University of Milan / Università degli Studi di Milano (Italy)
- University of Gastronomic Sciences / Università degli Studi di Scienze Gastronomiche (Italy)
- City, University of London (UK)
- University of Alicante / Universidad de Alicante (Spain)

- Research Centre of Institut LYFE / Centre de Recherche de l'Institut LYFE (France)
- Roskilde University / Roskilde Universitet (Denmark)
- University College Cork (Ireland)
- Atlantic Technological University, Galway (Ireland)
- Barcelona Supercomputing Center / Centro Nacional de Supercomputación (Spain)
- Instituto Superior Técnico at the University of Lisbon / Universitario de Lisboa (Portugal)
- University of Toronto, Scarborough (Canada)

9. Contact

All survey inquiries and concerns can be directed to the following partners, whose languages of correspondence include English, Spanish, and Catalan:

- Dr. Joan Ribas (Fundació Alícia): joan@alicia.cat
- Dr. Enric Bas (University of Alicante): bas@ua.es
- Dr. H. Rosi Song (Durham University): rosi.song@durham.ac.uk

The following sources can also be consulted:

- RELISH Cordis page: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101177427> or Project No.: 101177427.
- RELISH website: relisheu.org

10. Informed Consent for Survey Participants

The following text information will be made available as a “landing page” for survey participants on the application. Dates for survey responses requested after the first round of response by will be revised in the description within the granting period (2025–27).

[Below: Plain language explanation of survey and consent procedure for participants]

Thank you for your interest in taking this survey!

We are RELISH, a group of researchers working on a project about how food recipes and practices adapt to changing people and environments in Europe, today and in the future. RELISH is a project funded by Horizon Europe, a form of European funding that is awarded to

groups of researchers from different universities, research centres and community organisations across Europe on a topic that can benefit or improve society.

What is this survey about?

We created these questions to understand how your thoughts and everyday cooking or eating activities relate to the way that you live and connect with others through food.

By answering these questions, you will help us gain important insights about you and others' connections or interests in foods that might have national, regional, or personal significance. We're particularly interested to know if where you grew up, moved to, or who you eat with impacts these connections or interests, and how you see connections to food in your future life in a changing world.

What kinds of questions am I responding to?

We're asking questions in the form of multiple-choice, short and long-written responses. We're not going to ask you anything stressful or negative. It might be boring, but we hope that you'll have fun taking the survey!

How long is this going to take?

We think the first part of the survey will take about 15 min, and the second about 20 min. Ideally, we would like respondents to take both parts, but you do not have to complete and submit them at the same time.

We'd like to receive your responses by **December 15, 2025**.

What are my options when taking this survey?

It's totally up to you whether you want to complete the survey. We won't be collecting your name or contact info, or any specific information that could identify you. You should never expect any negative pushback from anyone on our team if you choose not to take any of the surveys.

If you do want to connect with us further after taking the survey, we have some options for you:

1. You can send us your email after submitting one or more of the survey parts to keep in touch with RELISH and participate in other activities we're up to. We'll make sure your contact info isn't shared with anyone except for the RELISH team, and your email won't be linked to your survey responses.

2. If you're interested in taking future surveys with us, feel free to bookmark this web application. The app will have up to date information about new surveys available for you to take. We'll also use it to update you about how your responses were used in our project!

Who has access to my responses?

We store your responses in a secure database to stop anyone from accessing or copying this data. Your individual responses will be anonymous and will only be seen by RELISH researchers.

We will never collect any information except for the responses you provide, and your email if you choose to provide this. Our team developed this web app, so no third-party can spy on how, when, and where you use this either!

What if I change my mind?

Right before you finish and submit a survey part, you'll get a brief message about how clicking "Submit" means you've consented to send your responses to us to use them in the way we've explained.

If at any time before clicking "Submit" you decide you don't want to provide your responses, simply exit the survey! Nothing will be saved. If you change your mind later, you'll have to restart the survey from scratch.

What if I want to learn more, or reach out to someone about RELISH?

In the survey interface, you can access links to learn more about RELISH, some technical information and links about research ethics, and the contact info for the team who is running this survey.

You don't have to take a survey to access any of these resources or get in contact with us—we're always happy to connect and chat about food and recipes!

What happens after the survey?

Your data is going to be used by our team to do a few different things: after we collect responses, we'll create visuals and preliminary analysis. You'll be able to see these on the RELISH digital platform at a later date.

Your responses may inform academic publications, workshops, exhibitions, or creative formats—always in a way that respects and protects your anonymity. We're happy to provide a

copy of any of these outputs to you, and we'll upload them to the RELISH digital platform for you to download or view as soon as they're available.

If you want, you can participate in other future surveys or opportunities to submit your experiences and food narratives to our team.

Ready to start?

Find a comfy spot and grab a beverage, then click "[Next]" to begin!

Annex II: Recruitment Materials

This Annex includes recruitment materials for disseminating the surveys to various social media, institutional, collegial, and public channels.

The first is a boilerplate email template for RELISH partners (see below). The second is the PDF flyer for survey circulation.

EMAIL RECRUITMENT TEMPLATE (ENGLISH): highlighted portions should be deleted in communications.

Subject Line: Three New Surveys for European Food Research: Participants Wanted!

Email Body Text:

****Apologies for cross-posting****

The **RELISH** (Reframing European gastronomy Legacy through Innovation, Sustainability and Heritage) Horizon Europe-funded research team is excited to share **three new surveys** for European food research!

These surveys seek to identify young people's perspectives on their food habits, traditions, and futures.

While we especially welcome responses from university-aged students (18+ years of age), anyone who has been living and working in Europe for at least 3 months is welcome to complete any/all of the surveys.

If you work with young people regularly, we invite you to also share the surveys widely in your networks. **[Optional to include for university listservs:** Instructors are welcome to share these surveys in their classrooms; feel free to offer extra credit to students who decide to complete them.]

More information about the surveys and ethics agreements can be found on the survey pages (links below):

- [Survey 1: Food & Culture Questionnaire](#) (multiple choice / short answer)
- [Survey 2: Futures Survey](#) (multiple choice)
- [Survey 3: Food Visions / Images about the Future](#) (short written response)

Further information about the RELISH project and funding can be found at relisheu.org and our [Horizon Europe project page](#).

If you have any questions about taking the surveys or sharing them with others, please don't hesitate to email one of the following RELISH members (languages of correspondence include English, Spanish, and Catalan):

- Dr. Joan Ribas (Fundació Alícia): joan@alicia.cat
- Dr. Enric Bas (University of Alicante): bas@ua.es
- Dr. H. Rosi Song (Durham University): rosi.song@durham.ac.uk

We appreciate your support, and thank you in advance for your participation.

Best Wishes **[or other salutation]**,

[Name/title],

On behalf of the RELISH team

See next pages for recruitment flyer.

NEW SURVEYS *for* European food research

Participants Wanted!

**Scan code for
survey links!**

Are you a young person
studying or working in Europe?

Are you interested in sharing
your perspectives on food and
the future?

Then RELISH wants to hear
from you!

Funded by
the European Union

RELISH is a food research project, funded by the EU.

Our team represents 12 universities and research centres across Europe and Canada.

We created **3 surveys** that will help us better understand young people's food perceptions and challenges in Europe:

- **Food & Culture Questionnaire**
- **Futures Survey**
- **Food Visions / Images (about the Future)**

Check out the survey pages for more info, or our website to learn more about RELISH!

Annex III: Survey Questions

This annex appends the corresponding questions and/or prompts included in all three surveys. They are attached in the following order:

- **Survey 1:** Food & Culture Questionnaire
- **Survey 2:** Futures Survey
- **Survey 3:** Food Visions / Images (about the Future)

Food & Culture Questionnaire: Tell Us About Your Culinary World!

Welcome! We're excited to learn about your food habits, cultural traditions, and cooking experiences. This questionnaire is all about discovering what shapes your meals, from daily routines to special occasions. Your answers will help us understand your unique food story, so feel free to share as much as you like! Let's dive in.

This questionnaire is part of the European project RELISH – Reframing European Gastronomy Legacy through Innovation, Sustainability and Heritage (reference 101177427), funded under the Horizon Europe program (HORIZON-CL2-2024-HERITAGE-01).

This questionnaire is anonymous. We do not collect names or personal identifiers, and your responses will never be linked to your identity. Data will be securely stored and used exclusively for educational, research, and cultural purposes within the RELISH project. The insights gathered may inform academic publications, workshops, exhibitions, or creative formats—always in a way that respects and protects your anonymity.

If you have any questions, please contact us to info@alicia.cat.

Thank you for your time, your voice, and your perspective. Let's dive in!

Section 1: About You. Let's start with a quick snapshot of who you are

1. Gender

Select one option

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say
- Other: _____

2. Age

Select one option

- 18 to 25
- 26 to 30
- 31 to 35
- 36 to 40
- 41 to 45
- 46 to 50
- 51 to 55
- 56 to 60
- 61 to 65
- Over 65

3. In which country were you born?

Select one option

Country Tab

4. In which country do you live?

Select one option

Country Tab

5. What is your current situation?

Select one option

- Working
- Studying
- Working and studying
- Unemployed

6. How would you describe your socioeconomic background?

Select one option

- Low-income
- Middle-income
- High-income
- Prefer not to say

7. Who do you live with?

Select one option

- Parents
- Grandparents
- Friends and roommates
- Partner
- Kids
- Partner and kids
- Alone
- Other: _____

8. Have you ever lived abroad?

Select one option

- Yes – **GO TO QUESTION 10a**
- No – **GO TO QUESTION 11**

9. Which country abroad have you lived in the longest?

Select one option

Country Tab

10. What is the longest period you have lived abroad?

Select one option

- Less than 6 months
- Between 6 and 12 months
- More than 1 year

11. To what extent did the experience change your way of eating?

Select one option

- Completely
- A lot
- Somewhat
- Little
- Not at all – **GO TO QUESTION 11**

12. Please specify what changed

Section 2: Exploring your connection with food

13. Do you follow any dietary preferences or restrictions?

Select one option

- None
- Flexitarian
- Vegetarian
- Vegan
- Gluten-free
- Dairy-free
- Halal
- Kosher
- Other: _____

14. When choosing what to eat, what matters most to you?

Select up to 3

- Health / Nutrition
- Sustainability
- Taste and pleasure
- To satisfy hunger
- Heritage / Identity
- Sharing / Socializing
- Convenience or ease of preparation
- Affordability
- Other: _____

15. How often do you eat in the following ways?

1 – Never 2 – Rarely 3 – Sometimes 4 - Frequently

- | | | | | |
|---|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|
| I make simple recipes at home | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> |
| I make elaborated recipes at home | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> |
| I buy pre-made or takeout food | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> |
| I eat out at restaurants or cafés | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> |
| I eat meals prepared by family or friends | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> |

16. Where do you usually buy most of your food?

Select up to 3

- Supermarket
- Local grocery store
- Fresh food market
- Specialized stores
- Online store or delivery apps
- Directly from producers or cooperatives
- Other: _____

17. What food items do you always keep stocked at home?

Select all that apply

- Rice, pasta
- Legumes (dry or canned)
- Nuts and dried fruits
- Snacks (chips, crackers, cookies, etc.)
- Ready-to-eat meals (pre-cooked dishes)
- Instant meals (quick-prep meals like instant noodles, dehydrated pasta dishes)
- Stocks, broths, or soups (bouillon cubes, liquid stock, ready-to-serve soups)
- Canned vegetables
- Canned fish or meat
- Frozen vegetables
- Frozen proteins (meat, fish and seafood)
- Fresh vegetables
- Tuber and roots
- Fresh fruit
- Dairy products
- Eggs
- Plant-base products (milk, cheese, yogurt, protein)
- Sauces, spreads, or dressings
- Other: _____

18. Who is mainly responsible for purchasing and cooking in your household?

Select all that apply

- Myself
- My partner
- My parents
- My children
- Another family member
- A roommate
- A housekeeper or hired help

19. When buying food or ingredients, what influences you most?

Select up to 3

- Health / Nutrition
- Environmental impact
- Taste and Pleasure
- Origin / proximity
- Heritage / Identity
- Convenience or ease of preparation
- Brand recognition
- Price
- Quality
- Other: _____

20. You're stuck on a desert island and can only eat one food/dish, what would it be?

Name three dishes you regularly eat

21. First, name one dish you regularly eat

22. Do you prepare it yourself?

- Yes
- No

23. Now, name another dish you regularly eat

24. Do you prepare it yourself?

- Yes
- No

25. Finally, name one more dish you regularly eat

26. Do you prepare it yourself?

- Yes
- No

27. Which cuisine(s) do you feel most connected to?

Check all that apply

- Spanish
- French
- Italian
- Danish
- Irish
- British
- Portuguese
- Japanese
- Chinese
- Peruvian
- Brazilian
- Mexican
- Arabic
- Other: _____

28. Where do you get information that influences what you cook or eat?

Check all that apply

- Cookbooks or magazines
- Parents/family
- Internet (e.g., Google, blogs, recipe sites)
- Social media (e.g., Instagram, TikTok, YouTube)
- Self-taught
- Classes
- Friends
- Immediate community (e.g., Butcher, Fishmonger)
- Restaurant
- Cultural background or heritage
- Other: _____

29. What are your top 3 food preferences?

Select up to 3

- Traditional family recipes
- Home-cooked meals and comfort food
- Street food
- Snacks
- International cuisine and fusion cuisine
- Fine dining or gourmet food
- Brunch-style meals
- Fast food
- Sweet foods and desserts
- Healthy or fitness-focused meals
- Other: _____

Section 3: Let's explore the flavours and traditions that define your food world

30. How would you describe your culinary or food culture?

- Personal or family heritage-based – GO TO QUESTION 26
- A mix of influences / fusion – GO TO QUESTION 26
- Regional (e.g. Catalan, Sicilian, Bavarian) – GO TO QUESTION 25a
- National (e.g., Spanish, Italian, Japanese) – GO TO QUESTION 25b
- Broader geographical area (e.g. Mediterranean, Atlantic, Nordic) – GO TO QUESTION 25c

31. You selected Regional, please specify the region

– GO TO QUESTION 26

32. You selected National, please select the country

Select one option

Country Tab

– GO TO QUESTION 26

33. You selected Broader geographical area, please name the area

– GO TO QUESTION 26

Name three iconic ingredients from your culinary or food culture

34. First, name one iconic **ingredient** from your culinary or food culture

35. Now, name another iconic **ingredient** from your culinary or food culture

36. Finally, name the third iconic **ingredient** from your culinary or food culture

Name three iconic dishes from your culinary or food culture

37. First, name one iconic **dish** from your culinary or food culture

38. Do you cook it for yourself?

- Yes
- No

39. Have you cooked or ordered it for others?

- Yes
- No

40. Have you eaten it in the last month?

- Yes
- No

41. Now name a second iconic **dish** from your culinary or food culture

42. Do you cook it for yourself?

- Yes
- No

43. Have you cooked or ordered it for others?

- Yes
- No

44. Have you eaten it in the last month?

- Yes
- No

45. Finally, name the third iconic **dish** from your culinary or food culture

46. Do you cook it for yourself?

- Yes
- No

47. Have you cooked or ordered it for others?

- Yes
- No

48. Have you eaten it in the last month?

- Yes
- No

49. Do these kinds of dishes reflect what you eat?

- Yes – GO TO QUESTION 31
- No – GO TO QUESTION 30a

50. Why not?

Check all that apply

- I can't afford them
- I don't know how to prepare them
- I don't know where to find or eat them
- They take too long to prepare
- I prefer other types of food
- No one cooks them for me
- I can't find the ingredients
- Other: _____

– GO TO QUESTION 33

51. How often do you eat these iconic dishes?

Select one option

- Regularly (once a week or more)
- Occasionally (a few times a month)
- Rarely (a few times a year)
- Only on special occasions
- Never or almost never

52. Where do you usually eat these iconic dishes?

Check all that apply

- I cook them at home
- Someone else cooks them at home
- At my parents' or grandparents' home
- At a friend's home
- At a restaurant
- At a takeaway or fast food
- At school, university or work canteen
- At a food market or street food stall
- Other: _____

Section 4: Your Cooking Style. Let's get a taste of how you work in the kitchen

53. How often do you cook?

Select one option

- Never – GO TO QUESTION 37
- Once a week
- Twice a week
- Three days a week
- Four days a week
- Five days a week
- Six days a week
- Every day

54. How do you feel in the kitchen?

Select one option

- I feel overwhelmed — I don't know where to start
- I prefer someone else to take the lead
- I'm not confident, but I manage
- Leave me alone, and I'll figure it out!
- The kitchen is my zone—I feel confident and in control.

55. When you cook, what's your approach?

Check all that apply

- I follow written recipes
- I watch recipe videos
- I rely on memory and experience
- I improvise as I go

56. How would you describe your cooking style?

Check all that apply

- Fusion
- Traditional / Classic
- Experimental / Creative
- Chaotic / No rules
- Survival / Quick / Simple
- Healthy / Balanced
- Comforting / Homestyle
- Trendy / Contemporary

57. Would you like to improve your cooking skills?

Select one option

- Yes
- No – GO TO QUESTION 39

58. What would help you improve your cooking skills?

- Tips and tricks about health, nutrition, and cooking
- Step-by-step video tutorials to learn techniques and recipes
- Weekly meal plans to build and practice different skills
- Cooking classes or workshops, online or in-person
- Mobile app with guided lessons and tips
- AI tool that offers real-time cooking advice
- Other: _____

59. Do you follow food/cooking/nutrition accounts on social media?

- Yes
- No **- GO TO END**

60. If yes, list up to three accounts (If it helps, go see three accounts you've recently saved one of their recipes)

Thanks for your responses

FUTURES SURVEY

RELISH PROJECT - HORIZON EUROPE 2025-2027

Grant Agreement: 101177427 – RELISH – HORIZON-CL2-2024-HERITAGE-01

Study Information

This study is part of the research conducted at **WP9 (futures scenarios)** by **FUTURLAB - The Foresight Laboratory** at the University of Alicante in the context of the RELISH PROJECT (HORIZON EUROPE 2025-2027).

Survey Purpose

This is a brief questionnaire about attitudes among young people regarding the future in the horizon of **2050**.

It's not about predicting - and being right or failing - it's about speculating about the future according to the information you manage and your own beliefs and expectations. It's **YOUR OWN OPINION** and **YOUR OWN PROSPECTS**. This is exactly what we need from you: your subjective and valuable contribution.

Your insights are very relevant and will directly contribute to the development and success of the RELISH Project.

Confidentiality and Data Protection

All responses will be treated with **strict confidentiality**. The data collected will be anonymised, securely stored, and used solely for the purposes of the RELISH Project. No personal information will be shared or disclosed outside the project team.

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION

Email Address: _____

Year of Birth: _____

Gender:

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary / Third gender
- Prefer not to say
- Other: _____

Nationality: _____

Country of Residence: _____

University (university of origin, if you are currently an exchange student):

Current Program:

- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Doctoral degree

Main Field of Study:

- Education
- Arts and Humanities (e.g., History, Languages, Philosophy, Fine Arts)
- Social Sciences, Journalism, and Information
- Business, Administration, and Law
- Natural Sciences, Mathematics, and Statistics
- Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs)
- Engineering, Manufacturing, and Construction
- Agriculture, Forestry, Fisheries, and Veterinary
- Health and Welfare (e.g., Medicine, Nursing, Social Work)
- Services (e.g., Tourism, Hospitality, Sports, Personal Services)
- Other: _____

FUTURE OUTLOOK QUESTIONS

1. How do you feel about the future of THE WORLD?

Scale: 1 = very pessimistic, 4 = very optimistic

- 1 - Very pessimistic
- 2
- 3
- 4 - Very optimistic

2. How do you feel about the future of EUROPE?

Scale: 1 = very pessimistic, 4 = very optimistic

- 1 - Very pessimistic
- 2
- 3
- 4 - Very optimistic

3. How do you see the future of YOUR COUNTRY?

Scale: 1 = very pessimistic, 4 = very optimistic

- 1 - Very pessimistic
- 2
- 3
- 4 - Very optimistic

4. How do you feel about YOUR OWN PERSONAL future?

Scale: 1 = very pessimistic, 4 = very optimistic

- 1 - Very pessimistic
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4 - Very optimistic
-

RELEVANCE OF FACTORS IN DEFINING THE FUTURE

Instructions: Rate how relevant each factor will be in defining the future.

Scale: 1 = totally irrelevant, 6 = totally decisive

5. ECONOMY

(Production, distribution, and consumption of goods and services within a society. It encompasses various aspects like trade, industry, and the financial sector. Economic indicators, such as GDP, unemployment rates, and inflation, etc.)

- 1 - Totally irrelevant
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6 - Totally decisive

6. POLITICS

(The governance of a society and its organizational structures. It includes institutions like governments, political parties, and other entities that make, interpret, and enforce laws and policies. Power dynamics, decision-making processes, and the allocation of resources and rights)

- 1 - Totally irrelevant
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6 - Totally decisive

7. CULTURE

(Shared beliefs, values, customs, behaviors, and artifacts that members of a society use to cope with their world and with one another. It's transmitted from generation to generation through learning. Aspects like religion, art, language, rituals, and social norms are part of the cultural subsystem)

- 1 - Totally irrelevant
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6 - Totally decisive

8. SECURITY

(Safety and well-being of a society's members. It includes both internal and external aspects. Internally, it deals with issues like crime, law enforcement, and civil order. Externally, it pertains to defense, foreign relations, and protection from external threats)

- 1 - Totally irrelevant
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6 - Totally decisive

9. ECOSYSTEM

(Biological environment and the complex web of relationships among living organisms and their physical surroundings. In the context of social systems, the ecosystem subsystem often focuses on how human activities impact the environment and how environmental changes, in turn, affect human societies. Pollution, conservation, biodiversity, etc.)

- 1 - Totally irrelevant
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6 - Totally decisive

10. TECHNOLOGY

(Refers to the application of scientific knowledge for practical purposes. It encompasses tools, machines, techniques, and methods used to solve real-world problems. In the context of social systems, technology can influence and be influenced by all the other subsystems)

1 - Totally irrelevant

2

3

4

5

6 - Totally decisive

Contact: ana.desouza@gcloud.ua.es

Institution: Universitat d'Alacant / Universidad de Alicante

FUTURLAB - The Foresight Laboratory

Thank you for your participation in this research study.

FOOD VISIONS/IMAGES (ABOUT THE FUTURE)

THIS STUDY IS PART OF THE RESEARCH DONE AT WP9 (FUTURES SCENARIOS) BY FUTURLAB- The Foresight Laboratory at the UNIVERSITY OF ALICANTE IN THE CONTEXT OF THE RELISH PROJECT (HORIZON EUROPE 2025-2027). Grant Agreement (2025–2027): 101177427 – RELISH – HORIZON-CL2-2024-HERITAGE-01

IT'S 2050. HOW DO YOU FEED YOURSELF?

DO YOU COOK? ...never, sometimes, rarely, occasionally, daily?...

HOW DO YOU COOK? ... simple? elaborated? improvised? using recipes? family ones or..?...

WHAT DO YOU EAT? ...veggie? paleo? varied? synthetic? nothing?; self-prepared?, ready-to eat?...

WHEN DO YOU EAT?... 3 (2, 1...) times a day?, intermittent?, once a week?, never?...

WHERE DO YOU EAT?.. home? work? street? restaurant? hospital?...

WITH WHOM?... relatives/family?, friends?, coworkers?, alone?...

Please, move yourself to 2050 and **IMAGINE**. Imagine how the world and your life will be, and write a **FREE-ESSAY**, a short story; "A day in the life in 2050" Sci-Fi style narrative, speculating about how a normal day in your life will be regarding food (cook and eat) in that hypothetical context. A journey in the future; like a post on a diary from 2050.

Please, write the story in **PRESENT TENSE** form (like a letter from 2050; like you were there/then)

IMPORTANT: Maximum 3.000 characters

EXAMPLE (just to inspire you):

It's July, 4th 2050, 8am. Today is my 45th birthday and I'm going to prepare a dinner for tonight. It's been a long time without cooking.. 20 years or more: I guess the last time I cooked by myself was during my university years when I shared an apartment with colleagues. I remember we used to cook simple and cheap things most of times, when not ordering something to Uber Eats (before the government banning sharing economy in 2030). So, it has bee a long while. But last weekend I found an old recipes book, handwritten by my grandma, at my mum's home. Many of the ingredients are currently not available or convenient, either because they have disappeared as species (like salmon, due to the sea temperature increasing), banned by authorities (pig, chicken), are unavailable (the commercial war with China broke supply chains), too expensive (like fresh fruits) or just fake products (raw cow is just an edible printed synthetic polymer, protein-fueled, that looks like meat but it's not). Anyway... I'll try to adapt my grandma's 1990s traditional recipe to our reality today and the existing ingredients. Well be 7 since I expect having 6 guests: my neighbor and his two wives, my ex (which I found in a dating app) and her human-looking robot (call it replicant), and my sister who is living in a Mars colony so she will be present in an hologram format. So, actually, and since the robot and the hologram doesn't eat physically, I have to prepare real meals only for 4; and buying a protocol fake menu for the robot and the digital simulation for the hologram... because an event like this is (still, like it used to be in our mediterranean culture) not about "eating" in itself but about sharing an experience instead. Etcétera, etcétera...

Confidentiality and Data Protection

All responses will be treated with strict confidentiality. The data collected will be anonymised, securely stored, and used solely for the purposes of the RELISH Project. No personal information will be shared or disclosed outside the project team.

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION

Email Address: *

Year of Birth: *

Gender: *

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary / Third gender
- Prefer not to say
- Other: _____

Nationality: *

Country of Residence: *

University (university of origin, if you are currently an exchange student): *

What program are you enrolled now? *

- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Doctoral degree

What is your main field of study? *

- Education
- Arts and Humanities (e.g., History, Languages, Philosophy, Fine Arts)
- Social Sciences, Journalism, and Information
- Business, Administration, and Law
- Natural Sciences, Mathematics, and Statistics
- Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs)
- Engineering, Manufacturing, and Construction
- Agriculture, Forestry, Fisheries, and Veterinary
- Health and Welfare (e.g., Medicine, Nursing, Social Work)
- Services (e.g., Tourism, Hospitality, Sports, Personal Services)

A DAY IN THE LIFE IN 2050: *

[Text box for response - Maximum 3,000 characters]

Annex IV: CSV Files

The following links bring readers to the locations where the public can view and download CSV files and preliminary visualisations for each survey:

- **Survey 1: Food & Culture Questionnaire** – https://relish.vps.tecnico.ulisboa.pt/youth_dashboard)
- **Survey 2: Futures Survey** – https://relish.vps.tecnico.ulisboa.pt/futures_dashboard
- **Survey 3: Food Visions / Images (about the Future)** – https://relish.vps.tecnico.ulisboa.pt/futures_narratives_dashboard